

Do we live in one single objective universe? The subjectivist challenge of Advaita Vedanta

Vinod Aravindakshan

Adjunct Professor,

Indian Institute of Technology – Palakkad, Palakkad, Kerala, India

vinodaravindakshan@iitpkd.ac.in

Abstract

The current scientific theory posits that there is one single objective world all of us inhabit. It also says that all the species existing in the universe grasp a small piece of this objective reality. The problem with this approach is that humans consider their perceived subjective reality as the one true objective reality. I argue that humans have no idea of the true objective universe and what it really is. All each person perceives is their own subjective universe where they are the observer. This is revealed by a simple example of comparing different perceived universes across species. The conclusion is that humans have no idea of the true objective universe, which is a mere figment of one's imagination. Using Science, each human confuses their individual subjective universe for the objective universe. In effect, all each human can ever know is our own subjective universe. Science rarely studies the perceived universe of other species, so the true objective universe will never be uncovered. Hence, all talk of an objective universe is a tall claim that is neither supported by logic nor experience. An Advaita Hindu based philosophical approach reveals more about the true nature of the universe compares to an imaginary science-based approach.

Keywords: objective universe, subjective universe, perceived universe, Advaita

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1. Introduction

Science reveals that we are but infinitesimal beings living in a possibly infinitely big universe. This is justifiably the right interpretation of the universe from an objective perspective. In the objective perspective, one studies the external world outside the body, and does not give anyone importance to the self, the observer. The observer is considered a necessary irritant. All observers are considered equivalent and substitutable with each other. Even observers across species are considered equivalent and substitutable with each other. This approach is absolutely correct from an outside-in approach, but from an inside-out approach, it makes absolutely no sense. Experientially, all living beings experience the world from an inside-out perspective. The subjective world is all we will ever know. Talk of an objective universe is a claim that is impossible to verify for any living being. Verification involves going away from the inside-out perspective to study the universe, which is completely impossible.

2. Thesis statement

A idea of a subjective universe is closer to individually perceived reality and one's own logic, compared to an imaginary idea of the objective reality that Science proposes.

3. Background

Hindu Advaita philosophy proposes an inside-out perspective of the universe. This altered perspective is exactly the same as lived reality. This is how all living beings experience the world. Instead of the observer being nameless, anonymous witnesses of an infinite universe; Advaita puts the observer at the centre of the subjective universe. Experientially, we know that this subjective reality is the only true reality we will ever know. By placing the observer at the centre of his perceived universe, this simple change in perspective makes sure that the universe is now subservient to the observer at the centre. Just as there is no observation without an observer, the observed universe is now conditional on the observations made by the observer, who is but you. This makes the observer the centre of his subjective universe.

This resolves many conundrums that modern science is unable to grasp or explain namely,

- 1) The idea of an objective universe runs counter to perceived experience. We perceive subjective universe instinctively. The objective universe is a model from abstract mental and mathematical models.
- 2) Individuals behave selfishly because they only sense their own subjective universe. If there was truly an objective universe where the living being is immaterial, selfish behaviour would be an exception and not a norm.
- 3) Human genetic behaviour tends to favour selfish self-centred behaviour consistent with the subjective perspective.
- 4) Humans think their every action count a lot in the universe, which would be bizarre if the universe is truly objective. Such incongruous thoughts and actions are evolutionarily

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viable only in a subjective universe rather than an objective universe (where the individual is infinitesimal).

- 5) There is no understanding why life did not correct for the discrepancies in perspectives of subjective and objective realities, if objective reality was the only truth. The correction could have occurred through genes or during information processing in the brain.
- 6) The objective universe is impossible by the Boltzmann Brain Hypothesis, which is a big problem for Thermodynamics and Physics. On the other hand, the subjective universe model is entirely consistent with the Boltzmann Brain hypothesis.

4. Arguments and Discussion

The idea of different perceived universes can be shown through this illustration:

Figure 1: Different subjective universes

What Science assumes as objective reality, is the circle P1 at the centre. P1 represents the generally perceived objective universe as per human understanding. It is based on feedback from the five senses. Touch, taste and smell are not critical for understanding the world. It is visual and auditory stimuli that are most important. For the general audience, visual information comprises 70-80% of the external world as compared to 20-30% for auditory information. There are a bunch of other universes in addition to P1

- 1) Birds and insects perceive Ultraviolet and Infrared light that we cannot perceive. Their universe includes our visual universe and a lot more. Their universe (P2-P1) is something we do not understand.
- 2) The world of lunatics in mental asylums (P3) is loosely connected with P1, but lunatics inhabit a world of their own. As much as Science does not consider those experiences real, they are indeed real to the individual. There is a small overlap

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between P1 and P3. People in P3 will not understand much of P1 and people in P1 will not understand much of P3. Both live in different worlds, alien to each other. Science has no idea what the world of lunatics is like, those the lunatics seem perfectly at home in those worlds. The world of lunatics is not a pure subjective world, it seems purely subjective only to a person on the outside. That subjective world is both real and objective to the lunatic.

- 3) Colour-blind people in P4 experience only a part of P1. Their objective universe is smaller than the objective universe of most people.
- 4) Blind people have an issue because sight captures distance more effectively than sound. Losing sight removes the rich and varied source of visual stimuli and that has to be replaced with sound. Touch, smell and taste need extreme proximity and cannot replace sight. What happens is that the region of visual perception in the brain is captured by the region dealing with auditory perception. Hence the auditory region expands and fills the gap in the visual gap. The objective universe of blind people is probably as rich as those of people with sight. How this happens, and the nature of the auditory universe is ignored by Science.
- 5) Bats perceive the world very differently from humans, by using sound waves. P6 has no connection to P1, but the objects perceived tend to be the same. How Bats reconstruct the universe and interact with it, is undeciphered by Science.

I have picked up just five examples, but there are millions more corresponding to each species. Every time, a new species is added, the objective universe grows further. This means that we have no idea what the objective universe truly is. However, we know that it cannot be just the universe perceived by the average human.

We find that scientists have never bothered to investigate the objective universe experienced by other species, including humans who are at the ends of the bell curve. The root cause for this failure is that Science has created an imaginary idea of one single experienced universe for all living beings, though that assumption is completely wrong and can easily be disproved like how I have done here. This misunderstanding of objective and subjective universes continues rampantly in Science among researchers. This is why the study of consciousness has never been taken seriously. Consciousness is the study of the subjective universe and there is no place for this realm in science today, because of a faulty assumption of one objective universe.

5. Counter arguments

First, is there a difference between perceived reality and the perceived universe? It is to be noted that the perceived universe is a subset of the perceived reality as perceived reality consists of both the objective and subjective universes. The perceived universe, on the other

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hand is only the objective external universe. The argument I have used here for perceived universes also work equally well for perceived realities.

Second, if subjective universes exist, how is it possible that different organisms and species can interact with each other effortlessly and seamlessly. For example, when the same prey is hunted by humans and a bird, the prey understands the intent of both predators and changes its escape tactics. Both predators also change their tactics as the prey change its own. There are three different universes at play here, and all of them agree perfectly well. How is this possible? One hypothesis is that of an objective universe which all of us are a part of. However, that claim is impossible to verify, as we have to jump out of our subjective universe to check that claim.

One of the greatest physicists ever, Erwin Schrodinger asked the same questions in his book, "What is life?" He wondered, *"Is my world really the same as yours? Is there one real world to be distinguished from its pictures introjected by way of perception into everyone of us? And if so, are these pictures like unto the real world or is the latter, the world 'in itself, perhaps very different from the one we perceive?"*ⁱ

Schrodinger also provides the answer to his own question, *"There is obviously only one alternative, namely the unification of minds or consciousnesses. Their multiplicity is only apparent, in truth there is only one mind. This is the doctrine of the Upanishads."*ⁱⁱ

Other philosophies have also tried to prove that the world is completely subjective, but have neither the flair nor sophistication that Advaita offers. They include

- 1) Subjective Idealism of George Berkeley: Berkeley proposed that the world is purely mental. Continuity is because of God. God is evoked only to solve philosophical contradictions. Since, the Abrahamic God is transcendental, it is not clear how another external construct can help solve the gap between external worlds and internal experience. An external God magnifies the problem rather than resolve it.
- 2) Transcendental Idealism Of Immanuel Kant: Kant proposed that we know objects as they appear to us (phenomena) rather than what they really are (noumena). At the same time, he said that noumena is unknowable, thus contradicting himself. If space and time are mental constructs, what explains the consistency of measurements. Schrodinger explained this problem well using Advaita, which Kant cannot.
- 3) Absolute Idealism of Hegel: Hegel's idea of reality as the progressive, historical manifestation of the absolute spirit or Geist. He held the Prussian state as the representative of God and acme of human progress. We can retrospectively, that such apotheosis of monarchy was meant to get personal favours rather than a real quest for the truth. Current Hegelian scholars hold that Hegel plagiarized many ideas from Hindu philosophy, especially Advaita, and passed them as his own without acknowledging the source.
- 4) Quantum Realism: Quantum Physics notes that the objective reality of the universe is not correct and that reality is also subjective in nature. It recognizes the role of the observer (consciousness) but has no meaningful theory to advance consciousness. Because Science deals with objectivity, Quantum Realism struggles to be both scientific

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and subjective in its approach. Eugene Wigner, Henry Stapp and Donald Hoffman are prominent researchers in this space.

6. Conclusion

The only logical answer to the problem of unity of perception in living beings, is revealed to be the unity of consciousness of all beings. This is Schrodinger's conclusion, copied from the Upanishads. This conclusion also ties in with the biological fact that all life arose from one common ancestor at least 4 billion years ago - Last Universal Common Ancestor. Life has never independently arisen since then and survived till today. We all derive our life and consciousness from this one ancestor. This unity of life as explained in the Upanishads may be the same unity of life we arrive at by molecular genetic analysis.

Science has to do a better job in studying consciousness and the startling results that arise from an in-depth study of philosophies that deal with it. In addition, Science has a deep contempt for religion shaped up by western conflicts between Science and religion. This animosity should not be extended to Eastern philosophies that are not concerned with God but with consciousness (Atman or Brahman). Scientists and researchers have to do a better job in integrating Upanishadic ideas to come up with novel hypothesis about the nature of reality.

7. References

ⁱ Schrödinger, Erwin. *What Is Life? With Mind and Matter and Autobiographical Sketches*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2012. p. 128

ⁱⁱ Ibid, p.129